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Editorial: Global solidarity for all generations

This issue features 16 papers on the impacts of COVID-19 pandemic on educational systems and society. Between all generations and cultures we need to work together to rebuild more resilient and loving societies. The consequences of the pandemic will continue to be seen even in the generation who are small children today. Intergenerational solutions are necessary and we need to spend more time to document the elements of communitarism that have been rekindled during this time.

Reinforcement of solidarity between all communities living in different parts of the planet will also be a lesson we can apply to mitigation of further climate change. Most of the papers were presented during the International Public Health Ambassador and Bioethics Conferences. There are going to be clear educational consequences for children at all ages of the educational system, and for adults, and these will get worse the longer our school lockdowns continue, together with abnormal social distancing. Ryan explores how indigenous wisdom may be useful to emphasize the importance of solidarity. Suma Parahakaran and colleagues, Eviota and Maboloc, and Bayod et al., present some of the educational consequences, and suggest some solutions. Quemado and Octaviano provide an example of a community extension program in schools in an indigenous community in the Philippines.

We have all had a variety of experiences during 2020, and Esra Bilir reports on the Turkish example of how the state facilitated the safe return of citizens from abroad. Chakraborty shares some reflections from the UK, and typical of many countries, the recent waves of COVID-19 have been even worse than the earlier ones. Manual and Migallos present a study of risky behaviour among children, as they felt less vulnerable to get sick from COVID-19. However, the essence of solidarity is that all members of society protect each other, and especially our vulnerable elderly members.

Bhuiyan et al. raise concerns of how vaccine roll-out in Bangladesh may be challenging given experience with other vaccines. Public information in Turkey is surveyed from Sukran Sevimli. There are mixed blessings from social gatherings in Pakistan described by Naheed Feroz. There are also two papers on the social issues of business communities in the Philippines. A return to battering as a form of economic exchange is one of many unexpected consequences of the pandemic. Please join the conferences to share in a wealth of information, and submit your papers to document more of our global lessons that will better prepare us for next time.

—Darryl Macer

Editorial address, and all correspondence to:

Prof. Darryl Macer Email: darryl@eubios.info

experience, teachers in the public schools find beauty in the mess, as in the form of unavailability of academic resources, connectivity and many others that cause discomfort and require a period of adjustment to cope with the demands of the pandemic. Their ways of maintaining psychological and mental health is to do more beneficial activities including the things that they enjoy, to relieve stress, like gardening, watching K-drama and selling flowers from their gardens. These teachers are living a positive and healthy lifestyle by getting physically active, getting enough sleep, and developing coping skills by eating healthy foods and drinking a lot of water, getting enough rest and sleep and doing light exercise at least three times a week, enjoying music and reading positive quotes in the social media.

They also emphasized that talking to god and to someone they trust are essential to staying positive and for mental health: keeping oneself calm, surrounding oneself with family, sharing feelings to others, reflecting on what the pandemic has brought them in a positive way and most importantly praying to god.

The advice of the teachers especially those who have experienced difficulties is to be compassionate with oneself and practice self-care. They emphasized not to deprive oneself from things or actions that can help forget the stress and struggles. It is best to have fun on weekends or during free time. It is also helpful to focus on positive things in order to stay strong minded, open minded and goal minded. And above all, never cease praying and asking for god's guidance to ease the pain and unload heavy feelings of uncertainty and discomfort brought about by the pandemic.

Indeed, these teachers have found beauty in the midst of the different mess they have experienced. Their stories will serve as inspiration to others, especially those who continue to wallow in pain and negativities in life.

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COVID19 and Challenges in vaccination programs in Bangladesh

Md Rijwan Bhuiyan ¹, Tandra Saha, Nazia Islam ², Tamsila Taramun ², Yousra Siddiquee¹, Maisha Ahsan Momo¹, Mahmuda Momtaj², Shahanaz Chowdhury ³

1. Dept. of Noncommunicable Disease, Faculty of Public Health, Bangladesh University of Health Sciences
 2. Dept. of Reproductive & Child Health, Faculty of Public Health, Bangladesh University of Health Sciences
 3. Dept. of Community Medicine, Faculty of Public Health, Bangladesh University of Health Sciences
- Email: dr.shahanazch@gmail.com

Abstract

The article tries to explore the current situation and challenges faced by the health system in Bangladesh regarding child immunization and also present the alternative methods adopted to make it functional. Data were collected from various secondary sources along with key informant interviews (KII) over the phone. The vaccination program is largely disrupted due to COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh. All static clinics remained open, but satellite clinics needed to be closed due to transport restriction and shortage of health workers. Overall, the

attendance rate is low in both types of facilities. Experts suggested to open the centers by maintaining physical distancing and frequent hand washing by health workers. The EPI division of the Directorate General of Health Sciences (DGHS) releases guideline. Vaccine shortage may create problem. Initiatives have taken place like solidarity flights, allocation of more funds and awareness building by developing partner. The reasons include transportation problems, health workers being affected by COVID-19, lack of PPE supply and awareness. The shortage of stock is another problem. A guideline has been prepared by the ministry, several strategies have been taken, like solidarity flights fly to import the vaccine. Effective action is needed to overcome this situation. Otherwise, the giant successes that have been gained over a long time in the country with tremendous effort may be ruined due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Introduction

The coronavirus outbreak was first detected in Wuhan, China in December 2019 with unknown origin. This is a highly infectious disease and symptoms include fever, cough, fatigue, shortness of breath, and loss of smell and taste. On 30 January 2020, World Health Organization (WHO) declared a Public Health Emergency of International Concern worldwide.¹ Although the cause is unknown, it is assumed to have come from animals and now it is confirmed that the virus has been transmitted human to human. Within less than 5 months from its first detection, nearly two million people from almost 188 countries are affected with this virus.² On March 7 the first COVID-19 patient was identified³ and as of 09 June 2020 there are 71,675 confirmed cases of them; 975 are died⁴ and the death toll is continuing to rise.

To reduce community transmission initially the government of Bangladesh banned most flights on 15th March.⁵ On March 26, country enforced lockdown included bans on travel on water, rail, and air routes and road-transportation was suspended. All non-essential organizations, businesses, and educational institutions are closed, except for pharmacies, groceries, and other unavoidable necessities.⁶

The immunization program in Bangladesh is a successful program and has been impressive in coverage.⁷ In Bangladesh the Expanded Program on Immunization (EPI) was launched on April 7, 1979 in a small scale and gradually was made available to all target groups (infants and pregnant mothers) by 1990.⁸ According to Bangladesh EPI: Coverage Evaluation survey 2016, from 1995 to 2016 the vaccinated rate reached from 76.0 percent to 95.1 percent.⁹

However, due to COVID-19 pandemic, the immunization activities are interrupted. Recent review of WHO and partners mentioned that this could put the lives of nearly 80 million children under the age of 01 at risk. Moderate, severe or total suspension of vaccination services was reported during March and April 2020 in more than half of 129 countries where immunization data are available. The director-general of WHO stated that "Disruption to

immunization programs from the COVID-19 pandemic threatens to unwind decades of progress against vaccine-preventable diseases like measles."¹⁰

The aim of this paper is to explore the current situation and challenges facing in immunization program during COVID19 pandemic, and to identify the alternative methods to continue the services and limitations that need to be overcome.

Methods

This study has combined primary and secondary data sources. The electronic databases PubMed, MEDLINE and Google Scholar were searched. A keyword search was also conducted in the Google server. We initially screened all titles and abstracts identified by electronic search and potentially eligible free articles were obtained in full text and abstracts for paid articles. Additionally, all online newspapers, documentaries, online/ television interviews, social media and blogs were included as data sources. All selected authentic articles and information were reviewed and addressed in this article with reference as secondary source of data.

Key informant interviews (KII) over phone and data from a few centers were collected as a primary source of data. As a written consent from the respondents was not practical, the interviewers' identity and opinions are presented anonymously.

Findings

The challenges faced by the vaccination program in Bangladesh during COVID19 outbreak have become a national concern. Stakeholders are trying to overcome these issues as a top priority and have started a dialogue. The findings are addressed based on data sources obtained below.

United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF)

They expressed that the stock is running low and there is a need to import immediately. Manufacturers also warned about the shortage from their side and a double shortage. UNICEF expressed that there will be no harm if frontline workers maintain proper distancing and hand washing during vaccination. Bangladesh has postponed national measles and rubella campaigns where 34 million children aged from 9 months to 9 years were targeted.

The DGHS has released a guideline to continue routine immunization during COVID-19 pandemic in line with UNICEF and WHO global and regional advisories. They mentioned the services should continue both in fixed and outreach sites as an essential service. UNICEF proposed to build knowledge, motivate, support and empower the health workers to protect themselves with frequent hand washing and other personal protection precautions so that they can continue their work. Additionally, there is a need to build trust in communities so that parents understand that with proper protective measures they can immunize their children safely. Also, it is needed to begin rigorous planning

to intensify suspended activities once the situation is under control.¹¹

UNICEF released a warning on their website under the title "Disruption of child vaccination in South Asia poses an urgent threat to children's health". Around 4.5 million South Asia's children miss out on routine immunization due to COVID-19 situation.¹¹ The UNICEF's executive director, Henrietta Fore said: *"We cannot let our fight against one disease come at the expense of long-term progress in our fight against other diseases; we have effective vaccines against measles, polio and cholera. While circumstances may require us to temporarily pause some immunization efforts, these immunizations must restart as soon as possible, or we risk exchanging one deadly outbreak for another."*¹⁰

World Health Organization (WHO)

WHO reported that more than 116 million infants are vaccinated globally. But there are still more than 13 million children who miss out on vaccination. However, this number will increase because of COVID-19.¹² The Director-General of WHO, Dr Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus says *"Disruption to immunization programs from the COVID-19 pandemic threatens to unwind decades of progress against vaccine-preventable diseases like measles."*

Around 14 vaccination campaigns supported by GAVI against polio, measles, cholera, human papillomavirus, yellow fever and meningitis have been postponed, which would have immunized more than 13 million people and the tragic reality is that children will die as a result. WHO urged countries to support Gavi's "ambitious goal" of immunizing 300 million more children by 2025, which will require \$7.4 billion in funding.

"GAVI" the vaccine alliance

"GAVI" along with WHO and UNICEF warned that COVID-19 pandemic disrupts vaccination efforts so nearly 80 million children are now at risk worldwide. Their report shows, out of the 129 countries, more than half (53%) reported moderate-to-severe disruptions, or a total suspension of vaccination services during March-April 2020. They explained the reason of disruption as parents unwilling to leave home, lack of information of the infection of COVID-19 virus and other health workers are unavailable due to restriction and in some cases shortage of PPE.

Dr. Seth Berkley, GAVI CEO stated: *"More children in more countries are now protected against more vaccine-preventable diseases than at any point in history, but due to COVID-19 this immense progress is now under threat, risking the resurgence of diseases like measles and polio. Not only will maintaining immunization programs prevent more outbreaks, it will also ensure we have the infrastructure we need to roll out an eventual COVID-19 vaccine on a global scale."*¹³ However, they called for joint effort to safely deliver routine immunization and proceed with vaccination campaigns against deadly vaccine-preventable diseases.

Online newspapers and other media

The issue has been publicly disseminated through the online newspapers. Before that it was under the discussion of concerned authorities. The *Financial Express* reported on 26 May, 2020 the headline "Pandemic halts vaccination for nearly 80 million children".¹⁰ The *Newage Bangladesh* reported on April 30 that *"Two million newborns and toddlers are on the risk of missing the schedules of 10 vaccines schedules"*.¹⁴

The famous Bangla newspaper *Prothom Alo* reported that about 1.9 million children are deprived from vaccination program due to COVID-19 situation in a Barisal division of Bangladesh.¹⁵ The *United News of Bangladesh (UNB)* reported from UNICEF that over 28,000 children under the age of five may die in the next six months as an indirect result of coronavirus pandemic in the worst-case scenario.¹⁶ The service utilization for children under five in March 2020 was down 25 percent compared to March 2019.¹⁶ This is due to nationwide lockdown, and delayed vaccine deliveries¹⁰; Parents are not bringing their children to the clinic for COVID phobia although the government has opened the static clinics.¹⁵ 26 thousand health workers related to EPI activities are providing services without PPE during COVID-19 pandemic. Till April 2, 2020 the government did not provide any instructions on how to provide service during the lockdown situation.¹⁷

Therefore, health workers have become anxious and agitated. Their association leaders proposed to stop the program unless sufficient protective equipment is provided by the government. Frontline health workers related to vaccine program in Moulovibazar district of Sylhet division were not provided PPE; therefore, they were at risk and some were not willing to provide services.¹⁷ Nearly 6 to 7 thousand static centers all over the Bangladesh are open except on Friday. Almost 1 lac 20 thousand satellite centers provide services throughout the country and these centers are in different houses, schools, etc. Some of the owners of these places were not willing to allow public gatherings during this situation, hence the health workers got in trouble whether to continue or open the center.¹⁸

Health worker reports

They have reported that although they attend the satellite clinics 4 days per week but less than one third did not present to receive vaccines.¹⁵ They also said that fever is post symptom of some vaccine, therefore, parents also become unwilling to take vaccine for their child as this symptom is similar to COVID-19 and may be taken as a social stigma. One reported even calling the parents from door to door they are not attending the clinics. Additionally, the place owners of satellite clinics don't want to allow the gatherings. Another health worker said she did not even get one child in the last two weeks under her 8 centers which is alarming.¹⁵ Health workers also said that due to this situation they are not able to fulfill their target and backlog is going high.¹⁹

Officials of EPI, Directorate General of Health Services (DGHS), Bangladesh

They said: "It has been a difficult task for us to run routine vaccinations in the current situation". The report concluded: They are about to run out of their stocks and arranging for a chartered flight to bring vaccines from abroad. Additionally, whether women aged 15-49 years and adolescents between 16-17 years are vaccinated with tetanus and measles, and rubella, respectively, is uncertain. The postponed measles and rubella campaign which targeted millions of children aged between 9 months and 9 years is in danger. DGHS issued guidelines to continue routine immunization during COVID-19 pandemic in line with UNICEF and WHO global and regional advisories.¹⁴

Key informant interviews (KII) over phone:

Information from various key informants was presented in a summarized way as we were not able to take formal consent and no one wanted to provide information other than in an anonymous manner. The overall findings are that the satellite clinics may open depending on condition. But the problem is that sufficient number of PPEs have not been provided to the health workers. Health workers reported that parents are not coming to the centers for service.

A few health workers reported that they got very successful result in terms of response. They would even call the mothers to confirm the vaccination schedule. The surveillance medical officers (SMO) reported that although the response rate is low in city corporation areas, in rural level presence is a little better.

Conclusion

The national vaccination program is largely disrupted due to COVID-19 pandemic in Bangladesh. Although static clinics are open, but the satellite clinics needed to close due to countrywide lockdown. The reasons are transportation problem, health workers are affected by COVID-19, lack of PPE supply and awareness. Overall, the attendance rate is low in both types of facilities. The shortage of stock is another problem. Healthcare facilities need to be ready for treatment, besides prevention of diseases, even during the pandemic. Also, it is a duty of the health system in general to make sure the panic caused by the pandemic is not outgrowing the demand for vaccination among parents of the target age group of EPI.

The health system needs to gain back the trust of parents and to encourage them to cooperate in executing the EPI by bringing their children to the facilities maintaining schedules. Awareness has been created through TV and social media for continuing the schedule with precision to make the parents bring their children. If needed extra camp and manpower should be added. Effective action is needed to overcome this situation immediately. The health system needs to gain back the trust of parents to encourage them to cooperate in executing the EPI by bringing their children to the facilities maintaining schedules. Otherwise, the success that has been gained over a long time with tremendous effort may be lost due to the COVID-19 pandemic. ^{22, 11}

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Reviving the ancient business model: The case of the Digos Barter trade during COVID-19 pandemic

- Fatima M. Chin

fatimamchin@gmail.com (Corresponding author)

Asia United Bank, Digos City, Philippines

- Raymond K. Hastings

hastingsraymond1@gmail.com

Cor Jesu College, Philippines

- Randy A. Tudy

randytudy@g.cjc.edu.ph

Cor Jesu College, Philippines

Abstract

Barter is an ancient charter before the advent of the cash economy wherein individuals and businesses use cash as a medium of exchange. During the height of the COVID-19 pandemic, the barter system, driven by social media's influence, suddenly resurrected. The purpose of this qualitative case study is to explore on the success of the resurgence of bartering in Digos City during COVID-19 pandemic. The case focused on the Digos Barter, a popular group of Digosenses with a strong presence on Facebook through its page named "Digos Barter Trade." Five individuals, including the administrator of the Facebook Page, participated in the Key Informant Interview (KII). Secondary data, such as comments and reviews on Facebook page and reports, were other sources of data. Results showed the drivers of the success on the resurgence of the Digos Barter Trade are unemployment, lack of cash, and a sense of community. Based on the results, the Digos Barter Trade members were driven by the loss of income and their need for socialization. The resurgence of the ancient business model during this recent pandemic showed how this model could fill in the people's physiological, social, and psychological needs in distress.

Introduction

The first form of commerce in human history was barter trading, a simple exchange where people could freely swap goods and services. With civilization, people needed more and more economic advances to meet their social needs. Hence, barter was not enough to meet the requirements (Rotolo, 2013). During the Great Depression in the 1930s,

the scarcity of money led to a revival of cashless deals (Kaikati and Kaikati, 2013). Consequently, people began bartering again; they exchanged work for food, goods for other goods (Rotolo, 2013). Barter is said to be on the rise again worldwide.

The Universal Barter Group (2008) reported that in 2004, 30% of all world trade came from barter trading; 65% of the fortune 500 firms engaged in barter trading in one form or the other. Almost one-third of all small businesses in the United States of America used some form of bartering. The Small Business Association (2008) stated that all indications show it increasing by the year. Barter trade is one of the tools individuals and firms use to survive during difficult times (Bazar, 2008). However, as commerce has become more complicated, slowly the barter system was fading away. But, when the COVID-19 pandemic hit the entire world, the idea of bartering goods resurrected.

The world is in the midst of the most severe pandemic that has led to increasing concerns and uncertainties (Ataguba, 2020; Weible et al., 2020). Nations responded differently, but with one common goal of fighting the virus. In the Philippines, this was by community quarantine. As the community quarantine dragged on for a while, individuals began to feel the burden of an acute shortage of goods and services that even led to hunger (Dutta, 2020). Businesses and individuals are thinking of ways how to address the problem. One of these is bartering of goods.

In the Philippines, bartering has been practiced long before the Spaniards colonized the country. During the COVID-19 pandemic, because of its impact on business and employment, it appears that bartering is back in time with a modern twist. A growing online community in Iloilo, Philippines has rediscovered the practice of barter or exchanging goods without money (CNN Philippines, 2020). In the process, many other cities followed, specifically in Digos City. The Digos Barter has about 44,000 members to date. Not only has bartering become a fresh way of securing goods, but it has also become fun.

The present study is our contribution to the literature on the resurgence of barter system, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. As this phenomenon is still developing, not much has been written about it. In this paper, we discuss the drivers of success for the Digos Barter Trade, facilitated by its strong presence in Facebook, a popular social media platform in the Philippines.

COVID-19 pandemic and the economy

The recent crisis, according to the World Health Organization (WHO), was declared a pandemic. Given the rise in the recurrence of pandemics, numerous researchers, including Garrett (2007), Keogh-Brown et al. (2008), Madhav et al. (2017), and Fan et al. (2018) argued that a largescale global pandemic was unavoidable. The Imperial College of London Coronavirus Response Team argued that COVID-19 is the most severe episode since the 1918 Spanish Influenza pandemic (Ferguson et al., 2020). Kuckertz (2020) stated that the COVID-19 pandemic